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User-centric and data-driven retrofitting solutions for a resilient, energy-efficient, low-emission and inclusive cultural heritage.

D1.2 – Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Summary

This Deliverable is the first report on Task 1.3. The D1.2 – Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the structured approach to handling research data within the project, ensuring its availability and usability both during and beyond the project's duration. This deliverable encompasses a detailed description of the diverse data collection, creation, management, and storage strategies.

A DMP is an integral part of Horizon Europe projects as it identifies what, where, and how the data will be stored in open access or restricted repositories and identifies results that will be the subject of dissemination and exploitation activities during and after the end of the project in compliance with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principle.

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifiers
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe

1. Data Management Plan

The EU project Herit4ages (www.herit4ages.eu) aims to develop and validate a set of technical and socially innovative sustainable energy and resource-efficient solutions, for the cost-effective improvement and preservation of the cultural heritage buildings.

During the Herit4ages project, research data will be generated, collected, and even reused. For Horizon Europe projects, a Data Management Plan (DMP) complying with FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) is mandatory. The D1.2 Data Management Plan (DMP) will be updated by all partners internally once a year, or whenever significant changes arise, such as when there are new data available; there are changes in the consortium policies; or there are changes in consortium composition and external factors.

The D1.2 will result in the revised version of the DMP, D1.3 “Data Management Plan (DMP) revised” at the end of the project (M48). The purpose of a DMP is to provide structured data handling and ensure the availability and usability of the research data generated or reused during the project and make it available beyond the project, whenever possible and meaningful. Hence, to organize and plan for making research data FAIR, this DMP includes the following information:

- Types and formats of data generated/collected or reused under different tasks of the project.
- Standards, formats, and methodologies adopted for data and metadata.
- Repositories adopted for storing and archiving data.
- Open accessibility, restricted use, and licensing rules.
- Curation and preservation of the data during and after the end of the project.

Horizon Europe, under the European Commission (EC), mandates a Data Management Plan (DMP) for all the data generated/collected or reused throughout the lifespan of the project. A DMP outlines the ways of handling, storing, and sharing the data both for open access and for restricted accessibility.

A DMP is an integral part of Horizon Europe projects as it identifies what, where, and how the data will be stored in open access or restricted repositories and identify results that will be the subject of dissemination and exploitation activities during and after the end of the project in compliance with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principle.

2. Data summary

The Herit4ages project consists of 9 work packages (WP), of which 1 of them deals with management, 7 of them deal with research and development, and 1 of them deals with communication dissemination and exploitation (See Table 1). Data will be generated under different work packages and for different purposes.

Data generated within the project will be given an open-access or restricted access. Table 2 answers the following questions on the data summary:

- What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?
- Will you re-use any existing data and how?
- What is the origin of the data?
- What is the expected size of the data?
- To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

TABLE 1 LIST OF PARTNERS, WORK PACKAGE TITLES AND CURRENT LEAD PARTICIPANT

Short name	Legal name	Country
TYN	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK – NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK – Tyndall National Institute (coordinator)	IE
CETIM	FUNDACION CENTRO TECNOLOGICO DE INVESTIGACION MULTISECTORIAL	ES
TESELA	TESELA MATERIALES INNOVACION Y PATRIMONIO SL	ES
IDP	IDP INGENIERIA Y ARQUITECTURA IBERIA SL	ES
FSMLR	FUNDACION SANTA MARIA LA REAL DEL PATRIMONIO HISTORICO	ES
UNINOVA	UNINOVA-INSTITUTO DE DESENVOLVIMENTO DE NOVAS TECNOLOGIAS-ASSOCIACAO	PT
UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	IT
FENIXTNT	FENIX TNT SRO	CZ
IBS	INSTITUTE OF BALTIC STUDIES	EE
CMF	CAMARA MUNICIPAL DO FUNCHAL (Municipality of Funchal)	PT
LWIT	SIEC BADAWCZA LUKASIEWICZ - WARSZAWSKI INSTYTUT TECHNOLOGICZNY (Lukasiewicz Institute of Technology)	PL
WUT	POLITECHNIKA WARSZAWSKA (Warsaw University of Technology)	PL

WP	Title	Current Lead Participant
1	Project Management	TYN
2	Definition of context and requirements for the design, evaluation, and validation of the solutions	TYN
3	Community engagement in conservation and energy renovation process for sustainable, accessible, and inclusive heritage	IBS
4	Herit4ages Digital Twin solutions	IDP
5	Energy sustainable integration solutions	UNINOVA
6	Herit4ages Renovation solutions	CETIM
7	Demonstration in real heritage context (Herit4ages Living LABs)	FSMLR
8	Evaluation and validation	TYN
9	Commercialization, dissemination, and communication strategy	FENIX TNT

TABLE 2 RESEARCH DATA AND ITS TYPE TO BE GENERATED IN HERIT4AGES PROJECT, P = PUBLIC, S = SENSITIVE

Wp	Identif. [task-nr +letter]	Purpose	Description	Type of research data	For whom	Software choices	Publication level	File type/extension	Max. Size
1	T1.1	Quality and risk management plan	D1.1 project management handbook	Text, tables, images	All	Word, adobe, excel	S	.pdf, .doc, .xml, .jpeg, .png	1 gb
	T1.2	Overall coordination, administrative and financial management and ethics assessment	Coordination procedures	Text	Consortium	Word, Adobe	S	.pdf, .docx	1GB
	T1.3a	Data management plan	D1.2 data management plan (dmp)	Text, tables, images	All	Word, teams / sharepoint, excel	P	.pdf, .doc, .xml	1 gb
	T1.3b	Data management plan	D1.3 data management plan (dmp) revised	Text, tables, images	All	Word, teams / sharepoint, excel	P	.pdf, .doc, .xml	1 gb
	T1.4	Implementation quality and risk management plan	D1.4 project management plan	Text, tables, images	All	Word, adobe, excel	S	.pdf, .doc, .xml, .jpeg, .png	1 gb
	T1.5	Liaison and synergies with the European Partnership on 'People-centric sustainable built environment' (Built4People).	Activities with B4P	Text, images	Consortium	Word, adobe	S	.pdf, .docx	1GB
2	T2.1	Multi-level barriers analysis	D2.1 study of multi-level barriers	Text, tables, graphs	All	Word, adobe, excel	P	.pdf, .doc, .xml	30 MB
	T2.2	Study of climatic, occupant comfort and energy usage in heritage buildings	D2.2 study of climatic, occupant comfort and energy usage in heritage buildings	Text, tables, graphs	All	Word, adobe, excel	P	.pdf, .doc	10 MB
	T2.3	Study of traditional energy retrofitting solutions	D2.3 study of the traditional methods and strategies used in heritage retrofitting report	Text, images	All	Word, adobe	P	.pdf, .doc	20 MB

Wp	Identif. [task-nr +letter]	Purpose	Description	Type of research data	For whom	Software choices	Publication level	File type/extension	Max. Size
	T2.4	Study demo site context	D2.4 heritage living labs context and requirement report and kpis	Text, tables, images	All	Word, adobe, excel	P	.pdf, .doc, .xml	1 gb
3	T3.1	Social baseline	D3.1 Social baaseline report	Text, tables, graphs	All	Word, adobe, excel	P	.pdf, .doc, .xml	50 MB
	T3.2	Herit4ages co-creation toolkit	D3.3 final report describing the co-creation toolkit used for stakeholder engagement in herit4ages demonstrations	Text, tables, graphs, images	All	Word, adobe	P	.pdf, .doc	30 mb
	T3.3	Social innovation and co-creation report	D3.2 report on social innovation experiments and knowledge transfer, including storybook on co-creation implementation in herit4ages	Text, tables, graphs, images	All	Word, adobe	P	.pdf, .doc	30 mb
4	T4.1	Demo Sites auditing and definition of Use Cases, Stakeholders & Roles	Demo Sites/Living Lab' auditing in terms of available data, models as well as any regulations that may affect Herit4ages implementation.	Text, tables, graphs, images	Consortium	MS power point, MS Excel, MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader...	S	.docx, .PDF, .pptx	50 MB
	T4.2	Specification of ICT architecture, stakeholder data requirements and objectives for Digital Twins platform	Define the ICT architecture underlying the Digital Twin Environment/Platform	Text, tables, graphs, images	Consortium	MS power point, MS Excel, MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader...	S	ppt, .pptx, .doc, .docx, .PDF	50 MB
	T4.3	Digital Data (BIM/CAD files, PDF Plans) of buildings	D4.1 hbim models and configuration planning	BIM model	Consortium	Autodesk tools	S	.ifc, .rvt	100 MB

Wp	Identif. [task-nr +letter]	Purpose	Description	Type of research data	For whom	Software choices	Publication level	File type/extension	Max. Size
		Living labs for HERIT4AGES DTE implementation and integration	tool for herit4ages living labs			Revit & CAD Any IFC viewer/editor			
4	T4.5	Exchange Information Requirements, Digital Twin Ecosystem, PaaS/SaaS	D4.2 herit4ages dt ecosystem (dte)	Text, tables, graphs, images	Consortium	MS power point, MS Excel, MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader...	S	ppt, .pptx, .doc, .docx, .PDF, .csv, .xlsx, JSON	50 MB
	T4.6	Exchange Information Requirements, Digital Twin Ecosystem, PaaS/SaaS, webAPI	D4.3 fully operational herit4ages platform and api with integrated tools and services	Document/tables defining data to be shared, type of data, units, etc. in order to develop API	Consortium	MS Excel, MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader...	S	.csv, .xls, .xlsx, .doc, .docx, .PDF	50 MB
5	T5.1	Technologies specifications	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	T5.2	Energy router and nilm development	D5.1 herit4ages energy router and nilm	Numeric, text, graphs, tables	All, uni, for control purposes	Matlab, excel, word, adobe	P	.mat, txt, csv, .xlsx, .doc, pdf	10Gb
	T5.3	Herit4ages green environmental development	D5.2 herit4ages green environmental sensor	Numeric, text, graphs, tables	All, uni, for control purposes	Matlab, excel, word, adobe	P	.mat, txt, csv, .xlsx, .doc, pdf	10Gb
	T5.4a	Integration of solutions	Usage of consumption and weather data for energy router control purposes	Numeric, text, graphs, tables	All, uni, for control purposes	Matlab, excel, word, adobe	P	.mat, txt, csv, .xlsx, .doc, pdf	10Gb
	T5.4b	Dynamic Data Integration	D5.3 integration results of advanced sensor and smart energy systems with the other herit4ages systems	IoT Sensor Data	Consortium	HTTPs, AMPQ, MQTT, and webAPI service	S	HTTPs, AMPQ, MQTT, and webAPI service	

Wp	Identif. [task-nr +letter]	Purpose	Description	Type of research data	For whom	Software choices	Publication level	File type/extension	Max. Size
6	T6.1	Preliminary assessment	D6.1 assessment living labs building materials	Text, tables, images, plots	All	Adobe, word, excel	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	T6.2	Material selection	D6.2 renovation products formulation	Text, figures	All	Word, excel	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	St6.2.1	Circularity approach	Sustainability assessment: lca and lcc	Figures, text reports	All	Word, excel	S	Pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	St6.2.2	Characterization and compatibility of new materials	Report	Text, tables, images, plots	All	Adobe, word, excel	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	T6.3	Modular panel production guidelines	Report	Text, tables, images, plots	All	Adobe, word, excel	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	St6.3.1	Modular panel production dosification	Report	Text, plots, figures	All	Adobe, word, excel	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	St6.3.2	Modular panel lab testing	Report	Text, plots, figures	All	Adobe, word, excel	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	T6.6	Fabrication of the prototype	Internal fabrication and testing report; in conjunction with d6.3	Text, images, spreadsheets	Cet, tyn	Word, excel, adobe	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
7	T7.1	Design of monitoring and installation at demonstration sites	D7.1 – herit4ages monitoring systems specifications	Gantt chart, text, tables, images, plots	All	Adobe, word, excel, sharepoint	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 gb
	T7.2	Installation of renovation solutions at demosites	Commissioning report; in conjunction with D7.2	Text, gantt chart, images	All	Adobe, word	S	.pdf, .docx	1 GB
	T7.3	Report on sensor installations and analysis of the data obtained through monitoring	D7.2 - monitoring report with the results of field testing of solutions and user's perception	Text, tables, images, plots, graphs	All	Adobe, word	S	.pdf, .docx	1 GB
8	T8.1a	Product formulations and sustainability assessment of inputs	D8.1 renovation products formulations and specific characterization report including sustainability assessment	Text, graphs	Consortium	Adobe, word, excel	S	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 GB

Wp	Identif. [task-nr +letter]	Purpose	Description	Type of research data	For whom	Software choices	Publication level	File type/extension	Max. Size
	T1.8b	Final sustainability assessment of the material solutions	D8.2 final report of environmental assessment of renovation solutions	Text, graphs	Public	Adobe, word, excel	P	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 GB
	T8.2	Evaluation report	D8.3 evaluation report of the social engagement, open innovation process and universal design	Text, tables, images, graphs	Consortium	Adobe, word	S	.pdf, .docx	30 mb
	T8.4	Resilient evaluation. Conservation and maintenance aspects	Report - d8.5	Text, tables, images,	All	Adobe, word, excel	P	.pdf, .docx, .xlsx	1 GB
9	T9.1a	Commercialization, dissemination and communication strategy	D9.1 dissemination and communication strategy plan	Text, tables, images	All	Word, excel	S	.pdf, .doc, .png	1GB
	T9.1b	Commercialization, dissemination and communication strategy	Promo materials	Text, tables, images	All / public	Adobe suit, excel, powerpoint	P	.eps, .jpeg, .png, .mpeg, .avi, .mpeg-4, .pdf, .ppt	N.d.
	T9.1c	Commercialization, dissemination and communication strategy	Website	Text, images	All / public	Squarespace	P	.html	N.d.
	T9.1d	Open access	All publications	Text, tables, images	All / public	Word, adobe	P	.doc, .pdf	1GB
	T9.1e	Commercialization, dissemination and communication strategy	D9.3 dissemination and communication report	Text, tables, images	All	Word, excel	S	.pdf, .doc, .png	1GB
	T9.2a	Exploitation and Ipr Management	D9.2 initial exploitation plan and ipr manual	Text, tables, images	All	Word, excel	S	.pdf, .doc, .xml	1GB
	T9.2b	Exploitation and Ipr Management	D9.8 final exploitation plan and ipr manual	Text, tables, images	All	Word, excel	S	.pdf, .doc, .xml	1GB
	T9.3a	Commercialization strategy	D9.4 the business model for herit4ages solution	Text, tables, images	All	Word, excel	S	.pdf, .doc, .png	1GB

Wp	Identif. [task-nr +letter]	Purpose	Description	Type of research data	For whom	Software choices	Publication level	File type/extension	Max. Size
	T9.3b	Commercialization strategy	D9.7 market assessment	Text, tables, images	All	Word, excel	P	.pdf, .doc, .png	1GB
	T9.4	Analysis of social aspects that need to be considered for commercialisation	D9.5 human-centered business model report	Text, tables, graphs	All	Word, adobe	P	.pdf, .docx	30 mb

3. FAIR data

The Herit4ages project aligns with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles for data management. The project aims to maximize accessibility to the dataset generated/collected within the project for its reuse.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Repositories

Data will be shared when the related deliverable or paper has been made available at an open access repository. The lead author will be responsible for getting approvals and then preparing the data and metadata for uploading on e.g. Zenodo (www.zenodo.org). The lead authors will also create an entry on OpenAIRE to link the publication to the data (www.openaire.eu)

Table 1 shows the data and its format that can be made available for open access or not. The data obtained as results from different deliverables of the project will be either sensitive (confidential, for internal use in the project), for public open access, or with restricted access, e.g. where IP issues or personal data must be protected.

Additional data not linked directly to publications will be included only if the partners involved in the specific task consider it convenient, and if it is compatible with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). For this purpose, the following repositories are used:

- **Zenodo** - an open dissemination research data repository created by OpenAIRE and CERN to provide a place for researchers to deposit publications, datasets, and other research artefacts such as presentations, code, posters, images, etc. Zenodo is funded by the EC via the OpenAire projects, CERN, Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, Arcadia Fund and donations via CERN & Society Foundation.

Zenodo currently accepts 50 GB per dataset (multiple datasets are allowed to upload) and there is no size limit on communities. Furthermore, Zenodo assigns DOI to every published record on its platform. DOI versioning is used to assign unique identifiers to updated versions of the data records, to make the data location unique, findable, and identifiable.

Herit4ages uses the Zenodo repository for open-access data sharing. Zenodo repository makes all related metadata publicly available, accessible and can be cited easily. Scientific articles as well as public deliverables and datasets of Herit4ages will be uploaded to this repository and obtain Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) from Zenodo.

- **Microsoft Teams and SharePoint** - Microsoft Teams will serve as an internal project data repository. A Microsoft Teams repository created by TYN serves as the primary repository for draft project deliverables as well as repository for intermediate (processed) data for access by designated personnel from project partners and for collaborating with all the partners in real-time and sharing files. The data will be stored by SharePoint within the consortium. Other partners can use their own repositories to store primary or raw data (e.g. monitoring from sites).

3.1.2 Naming convention

The naming convention is followed for the data related to publications or deliverables.

- Template: Herit4ages_[Del.#]_[DescriptiveTextDataset]_[Version]_[Date]
- [Del.#] follows the convention D[x.yy]
- Example: Herit4ages_D1.02_DataManagementPlan (DMP)_v01_30042024

3.1.3 DOI

Zenodo assigns DOI to every published record on its platform. DOI versioning will be used to assign unique identifiers to updated versions of the data records, to make the data location unique, findable, and identifiable.

3.1.4 Metadata

It is mandatory to provide metadata at two different levels: first, at the project level, and second, at the dataset level. Metadata at the project level describes the context (“who, what, where, when, how, and why”) behind the dataset to understand why the data are generated/collected and how are they used. Metadata at the dataset level explains the data and dataset in detail.

- Name of the project: e.g. Herit4ages.
- Dataset title.
- Project description: a short description of what the project is about.
- Principal investigator and collaborators: the person responsible within the institution.
- Contact information: contact person responsible for this project within the institution.
- Data abstract: a short description of the data collected, the purpose behind these data, etc.
- Dataset handle (DOI or URL).
- Data publication date: when is data made available: YYYY-MM-DD.
- Time period of data collection: start and end in YYYY-MM-DD.
- Keywords.
- Project funding: funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101123175.

- Version.
- Access: who should be given access:
 - sensitive, restricted internal: mono-beneficiary x,
 - sensitive, restricted internal: beneficiaries x,y,z...
 - sensitive, consortium: all members of the consortium/team,
 - open access, publicly available,
 - other
- Copyright: Creative Commons (CC) licenses considering open or embargoed accessibility of the data generated/collected. When the data is archived in the Zenodo repository, a license agreement will be applied to the data stating to what extent a user can use the data. There are different types of CC licenses with different characteristics as shown in Table 3 below. These licenses are widely adopted, easy to use, flexible and available in human and machine-readable forms.

TABLE 3 TYPES OF CC LICENSES AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

License	Copy/redistribute the work?	Attribute the author	Commercial use of the work	Adapt the work?	Change the license when redistributing?
CC0	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
CC BY	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CC BY-SA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
CC BY-ND	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
CC BY-NC	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
CC BY-NC-SA	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗
CC BY-NC-ND	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓

Dataset level

1. Naming dataset: as described in Section 4.1.2.
2. Data origin: experimental, observational, raw, or derived, physical collections, model, images.
3. Data type: text, spreadsheets, 3D models, software, reports, etc.
4. Instruments used.
5. Data acquisition details: sensor deployment methods, experimental design, etc.
6. Data file type: csv, mat, xlsx, tiff, dwg, etc.
7. Data processing methods: software used.

8. Data processing scripts or codes.
9. Dataset parameter list, with:
 - Variable names,
 - description of each variable,
 - SI units,
 - measurement accuracy, if applicable (mandatory for all measured results, not mandatory for simulation results etc.).

3.2 Making data accessible

All projects under Horizon Europe shall make all research data available for open access as much as possible while allowing for the protection of sensitive data due to commercial or security reasons. Complying with this open-access mandate of Horizon Europe, public deliverables, datasets, and publications will be uploaded to Zenodo repository.

The decision on the sensitivity (confidential) level of the data will be based upon the in-house assessment of the commercial vs. scientific value, in agreement with the consortium partners involved in the data generated through the consultation of the consortium leader and discussed with the specific people where needed. And if the conclusion to store in open access is agreed upon, then other project partners will be given 15 days to oppose it.

Data files with sensitive dissemination will not be shared. Data files can be added under restricted access in Zenodo with the possibility of sharing only when certain requirements are met. Such files will be shared only after the approval of the depositor of the original file. Data available for open access will be accessible using general software tools like pdf readers, text editors, spreadsheets editors, etc. If any software will be needed to read the data, then documentation about the relevant software will be provided and will be detailed in the corresponding metadata.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data produced in the Herit4ages project is intended to be re-used by other researchers, institutions, organizations, and across the countries. It will use common formats that are widely accepted and accessible using open software applications. Standard vocabularies will be used for all the data types and further explanations will be given in case of the use of uncommon terminology.

For interoperability, the format of the data is crucial. Proprietary formats for storing data used by commercial software may be critical, since there is no guarantee that data can still be read and used when the software is discontinued, and the data format is no longer supported by concurrent software products. For this reason, non-proprietary and open-source standards shall be used whenever possible. Where proprietary data formats are used, the mere possibility of losing readability in the future is a key element for excluding certain formats. In general, the formats presented in Table 4 are preferred.

TABLE 4 TYPE OF DATA AND PREFERRED FILE FORMATS

Type of data	Preferred file formats
Textual document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDF/A (.pdf) • MS Word (.doc, .docx) • OpenDocument-text (.odt) • Rich text format (.rtf)
Plain text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unicode-text (.txt)
Spreadsheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comma- and semicolon-separated values (.csv) • Tab-separated values (.txt) • Excel file format (.xls, .xlsx) • OpenDocument-spreadsheet (.ods)
Database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANSI SQL (.sql) • Comma- and semicolon-separated values (.csv) • Tab-separated values (.txt)
Tabular/statistical data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R (.R, .Rdata, ...) • PASW/SPSS (.sav, .por) • STATA (.dta) • SAS (.sas)
Image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg) • Scalable vector graphics (.svg) • PDF/A (.pdf) • TIFF (.tif, .tiff) • Adobe Suite (.psd, .ai, .indd, .aep)
Video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPEG-2 (.mpg, .mpeg) • MPEG-2 (.mpg, .mpeg) • Lossless AVI (.avi) • QuickTime (.mov)
Audio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MP3 AAC (.mp3) • WAVE (.wav)

3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

Herit4ages will enable interested third parties to access, exploit, reproduce and disseminate all public datasets for free. Data that has been published through open-access journals, made available in the Zenodo platform, or shared on the project's website will be accessible and useable by the third parties immediately after it has been published, i.e. after the approval of deliverables by the European Commission.

Data files in Zenodo can be deposited under closed, open, or embargoed access. Data files under embargoed access must be deposited with the end date for the embargo, and the one with restricted access will be shared only with the approval of the depositor of the original file. Creative Commons (CC) licenses are applied

in case of open access and embargoed access. Metadata in Zenodo is licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. For maximum dissemination, it is recommended to use CC Attribution (CC BY) license. This license will allow others to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon your work, even commercially, if credit is given for the original creation.

The public data in Zenodo is foreseen to remain for at least 20 years. In case of closure of the repository, all the contents will be migrated to suitable alternative institutional repositories. Since all uploads have DOIs, citations, links or data will not be affected.

4. Allocation of resources

4.1 Allocated cost

Herit4ages uses the Zenodo platform which is free of charge and hence no additional cost will be incurred. The costs for Herit4ages publications will be covered by the Herit4ages project budget as described in the Grant Agreement. All public documents will be uploaded by FENIX to the Zenodo repository. The responsible person is Anna Taťáková.

4.2 Curation

FENIX TNT is responsible for the elaboration of the DMP as well as for the data management in the project.

5. Data security

All the partners are individually responsible for their data security and preservation. All the data will be safely stored in their trusted repositories for long-term preservation.

5.1 Zenodo repository

Zenodo repository keeps data and documentation safe. All files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN'S EOS service. Each file copy has two replicas located on different servers. All uploaded data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies on different servers. In case of the closure of the Zenodo repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject-related repositories. Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

5.2 Microsoft Teams and SharePoint repository

To safeguard the data in Microsoft Teams and SharePoint, the requirement of two-factor authentication can be introduced. Data is mirrored in at least two data centers to mitigate the impact of a natural disaster or service-impacting outage. In case of a ransomware attack, version history can be used to roll back, and the recycle bin or site collection recycle bin can be used to restore. If an item is removed from the recycle bin, Microsoft call support can be reached within 14 days to access a backup.

5.3 Repositories of each partner

5.3.1 TYN

TYN, as part of University College Cork, uses Microsoft 365 services for the data cloud, such as OneDrive, SharePoint and Teams. A local repository (not connected to Herit4ages Teams and for use by TYN only) is used for modelling using dedicated software, according to the software licenses, and to store intermediate or raw modelling data. Access to the TYN repository and University College Cork repositories is through 2-factor authenticated username and password to assigned employees. Project personnel (including project partners) have access to the Herit4ages Project Teams through similar 2-factor authentication. Project repository access is through the Teams solution, with the University College Cork IT department managing its maintenance. The coordinator contact adds, modifies and removes guest users as indicated by project partners. Expected data storage of project data is at least 5 years after project finalization.

5.3.2 CETIM

CETIM has its own server system to storage data. Dedicated folders have been created with access limited to the different staff involved in the project including Project Management, Technical Staff and Financial Officers. Access is limited to employees; access is restricted to certain employees assigned with a role in the project.

5.3.3 TESELA

TESELA is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A folder for Herit4ages has been established on the TESELA SharePoint platform and only a few members of TESELA have access to it. In addition, access is more tightly controlled than on the main project site, with a dedicated folder for research datasets.

The person responsible for data management of the Herit4ages project at TESELA is Gaspar Carrasco-Huertas.

5.3.4 IDP

IDP has its own server system to store data and uses Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A folder for Herit4ages has been established on the IDPs SharePoint platform and selected members have access to it. All the project documentation will be stored in the project shared folder.

5.3.5 FSMLR

FSMLR is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A folder for Herit4ages has been established on the FSMLR SharePoint platform and selected members of the Foundation have access to it. All physical documents containing data collected throughout the project (e.g., questionnaires and surveys conducted with stakeholders) will be stored in secure repositories located at the facilities of Fundación Santa

María la Real, at Avenida Ronda, 1, 34800 Aguilar de Campoo, Palencia, Spain. The duration of this data storage will be 5 years.

The person responsible for data management of the Herit4ages project at FSMLR is Javier Fuertes Cabero.

5.3.6 UNINOVA

UNINOVA will store the data acquired in the Funchal pilot on its own servers at UNINOVA's location. Access will be restricted, and data can be shared upon Funchal pilot tenants' consent.

The person responsible for data management of the Herit4ages project at UNINOVA is Pedro Pereira.

5.3.7 UNIBO

UNIBO is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A dedicated folder for Herit4Ages has been established on the UNIBO SharePoint platform and only a few members of the UNIBO's research group have access to it. All physical documents containing data collected throughout the project (e.g., questionnaires and surveys conducted with stakeholders) will be stored in this repository throughout the duration of the project and/or the time necessary to carry out the research activities and their dissemination.

Furthermore, the AMS Acta (UNIBO institutional repository, <https://amsacta.unibo.it/>) and Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) will be used to publicly publish a selection of datasets used in the research in open access, in accordance with the data privacy regulations of the Herit4Ages project and the University of Bologna and after consulting the project's coordinator.

The person responsible for data management of the Herit4Ages project at UNIBO is Angelo Massafra.

5.3.8 FENIXTNT

FENIX is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A dedicated site for Herit4ages has been established on the FENIX SharePoint platform and can be accessed only by the partner representatives in the consortium. Furthermore, a dedicated folder for research datasets is set up, allowing for stricter access control than the main project site. All public documents will be shared on the Herit4ages project website and ZENODO, and sensitive reports on the Herit4ages server.

The person responsible for the data management of the Herit4ages project is Petra Colantonio.

5.3.9 IBS

IBS is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A dedicated site for Herit4ages has been established on the IBS SharePoint platform and access to the site is restricted to members of the project team at IBS, using 2-factor authentication.

The person responsible for the data management of the Herit4ages project is Merit Tatar (DPO of IBS in general is Kristjan Kaldur).

5.3.10 CMF

CMF is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A dedicated folder for Herit4Ages has been established on the UNIBO SharePoint platform and only a few members of the CMF partner have access to it.

The person responsible for data management of the Herit4ages project at CMF is José Silvestre Franco.

5.3.11 LWIT

LWIT is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A dedicated site for Herit4ages has been established on the LWIT SharePoint platform and can be accessed only by the partner representatives in the consortium. In parallel, LWIT, as a public research institute, is legally obliged to store data and documents in a limited access, secure electronic system compliant with Head Office of State Archives of Poland guidelines and archive management laws (in this case - on-prem EZD PUW archive management system).

The person responsible for data management of the Herit4Ages project at LWIT is Jakub Kalitowski.

5.3.12 WUT

WUT is using Microsoft 365 services for OneDrive, SharePoint, and Teams. A dedicated working team for Herit4Ages has been established on the WUT teams platform and only a few members of the WUT's research group have access to it. All physical documents containing data collected throughout the project will be stored in this repository throughout the duration of the project and/or the time necessary to carry out the research activities and their dissemination.

The person responsible for data management of the Herit4Ages project at WUT is Anna Nowak.

6. Annexes

6.1 Data Requirements Questionnaire

The following questionnaire is to be completed by all the partners to gather information about the data requirements for carrying out DMP under FAIR principles. The questionnaire in this section is taken from the DMP template recommended under Horizon Europe. The completed questionnaire is to be shared with the partners responsible for the data management (FENIX) and is to be saved in the internal project repository as well. Additionally, it is to be made available to the European Commission upon their request.

6.1.1 Data summary

Table 5 is a template to be filled out by each member of the consortium and reported in Table 2.

TABLE 5 RESEARCH DATA AND ITS TYPE TO BE GENERATED IN HERIT4AGES PROJECT

WP	Identif. [Task-Nr/subT-Nr.]	Purpose	Description	Type of research data	For whom	Software choices	Publication level	File type / extension	Max. size
Work package number	e.g. T4.2a/ST4.2.1	Objective of generating/ Collecting the data	e.g. Test results of the experiment	e.g. test data in .xlsx, images	People foreseen to use the data later	Software considered for the corresponding data e.g. Excel	To be published or not (Yes, no or publishing with restricted access)	Whether in .xlsx, .csv, .pdf, .R, .dwg, etc.	n MB, GB, etc

6.1.2 Additional questions to be answered by each partner

All partners in the consortium answered the questions below as part of the questionnaire template. The answers can be found in Sections 6.2.1 – 6.2.12.

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

6.1.3 Ethical aspects

All partners in the consortium answered the questions below as part of the questionnaire template. The answers can be found in Sections 6.2.1 – 6.2.12.

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.2 Results of Data Requirements Questionnaire

6.2.1 TYN

<p>Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?</p>
<p>Data which is considered by the principal investigator to have potential for IP protection is discussed with the Technology Transfer Officer (TTO) of University College Cork (UCC). In case of further doubts, the legal department of TYN is consulted for IP legal matters. Other type of data will follow the Grant Agreement level of confidentiality. Intermediate data which does not have IP potential might also be kept confidential by the principal investigator in order to avoid confusion when it is refined.</p>
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?</p>
<p>Staff at TYN involved in the project has shared responsibility, overseen by the UCC Data Protection Officer (DPO)</p>
<p>Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?</p>
<p>Yes</p>
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>
<p>For locally generated data, servers at TYN can be accessed by authorized personnel only through username and password. Safety copies are made periodically. UCC provides a cloud storage solution that is also accessed through authenticated username and password</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?</p>
<p>Long term preservation is envisioned in the UCC cloud storage solution.</p>
<p>Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).</p>
<p>Any data with personal identifiers or that can identify a person must be made anonymous or pseudo-anonymized in order to comply with GDPR. Any data which is considered to have potential for IP protection will follow the guidelines for further exploitation and sharing detailed in the Consortium Agreement. Data that does not fall into any of these categories can be shared on open repositories.</p>
<p>Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>
<p>Yes with reference to the UCC's DPO for further doubts or contacts, including time of preservation and possibility to withdraw</p>

6.2.2 CETIM

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
First, technical staff communicates with project management (EU Projects Office) about the data to be released, any potential IPR conflict is analysed. Secondly, the release of information is checked with project coordinators and consortium following the GA rules. If both control spots are passed data can be made accessible.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Technical staff of CETIM is responsible of Data Management with the support of EU Projects Office.
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
Yes
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
Controls on data release are implemented as described in the first question. CETIM servers have periodical safety copies to ensure any potential conflict on data storage.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Depending on project policies.
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Yes, as part of a legal disclaimer in the organisation, but it is not the case of this project in relation with CETIM's activities.

6.2.3 TESELA

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
In agreement with the consortium partners who provide the data, through consultation of the consortium leader and discussed with specific people where needed.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Gaspar Carrasco-Huertas – gasparcarrasco@teselainnova.com
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
-
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
All TESELA data are stored securely, with restricted access to cloud-based services (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint) for recovery, accessibility, and security. All data related to Herit4ages will be stored in the repository indefinitely unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes. The data will be safely stored in trusted repositories located at TESELA SharePoint.
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No ethical or legal issues.
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
TESELA uses GDPR compliant procedures.

6.2.4 IDP

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
In agreement with the consortium partners who provide the data, through consultation of the consortium leader and discussed with specific people where needed.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Mikel Borrás - mborras@idp.es
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
-
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
All IDP data are stored securely, with restricted access to cloud-based services (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint) for recovery, accessibility, and security. All data related to Herit4ages will be stored in the repository indefinitely unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes. The data will be safely stored in the project shared folder, as well as at the IDP's SharePoint.
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No ethical or legal issues.
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
IDP uses GDPR compliant procedures.

6.2.5 FSMLR

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
In agreement with the consortium partners who provide the data, through consultation of the consortium leader and discussed with specific people where needed.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Javier Fuertes Cabero - jfuertes@santamarialareal.org
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
-
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
All FSMRL data are stored securely, with restricted access to cloud-based services (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint) for recovery, accessibility, and security. All data related to Herit4ages will be stored in the repository for as long as necessary to fulfil the purposes for which they were obtained, unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes. All documents will be stored in secure repositories located at the premises of Fundación Santa María la Real, at Avenida Ronda, 1, 34800 Aguilar de Campoo, Palencia, Spain. The duration of this data storage will be 5 years.
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No ethical or legal issues.
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Yes. FSMLR uses GDPR compliant procedures.

6.2.6 UNINOVA

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
In agreement with the consortium partners who provide the data (namely the tenant at the Funchal pilot), through consultation of the consortium leader and discussed with specific people where needed.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Pedro Pereira – pmp@fct.unl.pt
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
UNINOVA can store the Funchal pilot data for 5 years, free of charge.
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
All Funchal pilot data is stored securely, with restricted access for recovery, accessibility, and security purposes.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes, for a period of 5 years.
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No ethical issues are foreseen. Data can be shared upon consent from Funchal Pilot tenants.
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Yes

6.2.7 UNIBO

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
The confidentiality level of the data will be decided among the UNIBO’s team members in consultation with consortium leaders and partners.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Angelo Massafra – angelo.massafra2@unibo.it
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
Data preservation will be provided free of charge when data is deposited in the AMS Acta institutional repository. The data will be retained for the duration of the project and/or until all project dissemination activities are concluded.
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
Backup, data recovery, security, and accessibility activities will be entrusted to cloud services with restricted access (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint). Furthermore, UNIBO will perform periodic backups on local data storage devices.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No ethical or legal issues
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Yes, UNIBO uses GDPR compliant procedures

6.2.8 FENIXTNT

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
In agreement with the consortium partners who provide the data, through consultation of the consortium leader and discussed with specific people where needed.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Petra Colantonio – petra.colantonio@fenixtnt.cz
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
-
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
All FENIX data are stored securely, with restricted access to cloud-based services (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint) for recovery, accessibility, and security. All data related to Herit4ages will be stored in the repository indefinitely unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes.
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No ethical or legal issues.
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
FENIX uses GDPR compliant procedures.

6.2.9 IBS

<p>Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?</p>
<p>First, IBS will follow the level of confidentiality for project deliverables stated in the Grant Agreement. As a rule, all deliverables and datasets that do not involve personal, confidential or IP-protected data will be made open access. In case of doubts, project staff will consult the DPO of IBS, consortium leader and relevant partners to determine the appropriate level of access, including possibilities of providing open access only to such parts of the datasets that do not include protected data.</p>
<p>Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?</p>
<p>Merit Tatar (involving DPO of IBS Kristjan Kaldur, if necessary)</p>
<p>Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?</p>
<p>Yes</p>
<p>What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?</p>
<p>All project data are stored securely on Microsoft 365 cloud services (SharePoint, OneDrive, Teams) and are only accessible to authorized project team members at IBS. Multi-factor authentication is used for increased security. Risks of data loss and corruption are mitigated by built-in auto-save and auto-recovery features of the Microsoft 365 services.</p>
<p>Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?</p>
<p>Data will be stored at the Microsoft 365 cloud-based file storage for the duration of the project and at least 5 years after the end of the project. Open-access deliverables and datasets will be uploaded to the Zenodo open research data repository for long-term preservation.</p>
<p>Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).</p>
<p>Some data collected in relation to stakeholder engagement in demonstrations may include personal data. Informed consent procedures will be used to ensure data subjects' control over the use of their data. As a rule, personal data will not be shared with parties outside the project team and will only be shared in an anonymized form.</p>
<p>Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>
<p>IBS uses GDPR compliant procedures for obtaining informed consent, including detailed information on the purpose of data processing and possibilities to withdraw consent.</p>

6.2.10 CMF

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
The confidentiality level of the data will be decided among the CMF team members in consultation with consortium leader and partners.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
José Silvestre Franco
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
-
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
All CMF data are stored securely, with restricted access to cloud-based services (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint) for data, recovery, accessibility, and security. All data will be stored indefinitely unless otherwise agreed in contracts. CMF will do periodic backups on local data storage devices.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes.
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No.
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Yes. CMF uses GDPR compliant procedures.

6.2.11 LWIT

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
In agreement with the consortium partners who provide the data, through consultation of the consortium leader and discussed with specific people where needed.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Jakub Kalitowski, e-mail: jakub.kalitowski@wit.lukasiewicz.gov.pl
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
Data preservation will be provided for the duration of the project and/or until all the project dissemination activities are finalised free of charge when the data is repositied in EZD PUW data management system.
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
All LWIT data is stored securely, with restricted access to cloud-based services (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint) and on-prem data management system (EZD PUW) for recovery, accessibility, and security. All data related to Herit4ages will be stored in the repository for as long as necessary to fulfil the purposes for which they were obtained, unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No ethical or legal issues foreseen.
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Yes, LWIT uses GDPR compliant procedures.

6.2.12 WUT

Which is the procedure for deciding the confidentiality level of the data and for making data open access / restricted access?
The confidentiality level of the data will be decided among the WUT's team members in consultation with consortium leaders and partners if it will be needed.
Who will be responsible for data management in your tasks of the project?
Anna Nowak (anna.nowak@pw.edu.pl)
Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?
The data will be retained for the duration of the project and/or until all project dissemination activities are concluded. After ending the project data will be a part of local data storage devices of Centre for Universal Design at WUT.
What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
Backup, data recovery, security, and accessibility activities will be entrusted to cloud services with restricted access (OneDrive, Teams, SharePoint). Furthermore, WUT will perform periodic backups on local data storage devices.
Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?
Yes
Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
No
Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?
Yes, WUT uses GDPR (RODO) compliant procedures

